

What makes software FAIR? Reviewing the Towards FAIR Principles for Research Software paper and new research related to FAIR software: A report from FAIR4RS Subgroup 4

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Introduction

This report summarises the work of the FAIR for Research Software Subgroup 4, which was tasked with reviewing the Towards FAIR Principles for Research Software paper and identifying new research that had been published after that paper was written.

This draft report is still subject to revision.

Survey

A survey was circulated to the subgroup, as well as further afield, that asked some general questions around FAIR for research software along with specific questions about the suitability of the principles presented in the Towards FAIR Principles for Research Software.

This report summarises and analyses the results of the survey.

New research on FAIR software

Twenty-five suggestions of relevant new research were collected. A gap that was identified was the absence of key works from other disciplines, such as social sciences. The full bibliography has been published separately [\[1\]](#).

Definition of FAIR software

The following characteristics were suggested as being potential markers of FAIR software:

- Its metadata
 - Software is named
 - Software has a version number
- How and where it is shared/published
 - Online, publicly accessible repository (FAIR)
 - “Available on request” (unFAIR)
- The amount of usage / users
- Published and described in a peer-reviewed article
- Dependencies listed
- Citable and cited
- Well documented (FAIR) / poorly documented (unFAIR)
- Licensing - specifically open source (FAIR) or things that prevent reuse or re-engineering (unFAIR)
- If it's still maintained and someone is responsible
- Ability to reuse in the future
- Versioned

The following software were given as examples of “FAIR” software:

- Git
- HDF5
- NumPy
- SciPy
- SQLite
- Pandas
- [DataLad](#)
- [OcamlP3I release 2.03](#) - as it has followed the reproducibility challenge described in this article: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4041602>
- Galaxy
- [NetLogo](#)

The following software were given as examples of “unFAIR” software:

- Gnuplot - previously, because the license made it hard to renew
- Numerical recipes code (F and A but hard to reuse because of licensing)
- ARCGIS (commercial licensing)
- NVivo
- [COVID-SIM](#) - because it doesn't have a PID (or the PID isn't shown on the citation) and it is not archived.
- Software that is "available upon request to the authors"
- “One run only” software and scripts - as it isn't clear if anyone is responsible, is still maintained or version-controlled.
- Spreadsheets

One common response was that commercial / closed source software was not FAIR.

Can the FAIR principles be applied to software?

Can the FAIR principles be applied to software?

32 responses

Some of the responses which were noted from people who answered “Yes, but the four foundational principles do not adequately reflect software / there are additional foundational principles that are missing” include:

- FAIR is secondary to the important good practices we need around software
- FAIR ratings for components can only be made in the context of a specific stack. Otherwise, NumPy would be criticized for not being interoperable with R.
- Long term preservation is not reflected in FAIR
- It's unclear where dependencies should be addressed
- Software consists of large stacks of interdependent components which means that different criteria must be applied at different levels
- Software is authored by humans for a purpose, in contrast to most data that represents observations of the outside world
- A missing principle is sustainability: to what degree is maintenance ensured by supporting organizations, and how much maintenance effort is required by clients adopting the software as a dependency?

A particular response that was seen multiple times is that the FAIR principles need to be applied recursively, i.e. a piece of software that depends on others can only be as FAIR as its dependencies.

One respondent proposed a new principle of “dependable”. Dependable software is software you can build on - other software, but also research projects.

- D1. The software is maintained by a large community, or supported an institution that has made a long-term commitment to its maintenance.
- D2. The software comes with a policy statement about its future evolution (backward compatibility, supported platforms, etc.)
- D3. The software's dependencies are as dependable as the software itself.

A particularity of dependability is that it's not universally "good". Much scientific software doesn't need to be dependable. For example the scripts that produce the plots for a paper. Dependability is a criterion for infrastructure software.

FAIR for software

The remainder of this report summarises the responses to questions asking about individual foundational and guiding principles. Responses on the definition of the foundational principles are followed by a table for each foundational principle showing the percentages of respondents agreeing with the statement of each guiding principle, along with individual suggestions for changes.

Findable

What does findability mean in the context of software?

- Software in registry / package manager / repository with associated metadata
- Software mentioned in associated / related research objects (publications, data, software etc) is findable
- Ability to find existing software that fulfils a purpose (as described by metadata), including support for search engines.
- Features / properties / requirements of software searchable in database.
- Find the exact / unambiguous version of a piece of software using an identifier.
- Machine readable software directories with features.
- Authoritative repositories.
- Searchable repositories.
- Easy to obtain (source code and executable) [Accessible?]
- Includes documentation, input/output, dependencies [Recursive?]
- Narrow wording of “software” excludes objects on the boundary of “software”
- See functional package management with Nix that solves all of these questions automatically in a principled way. Also check out the unison web project that goes one step further.
- Different DOI's from different platforms create a myriad of "unique identifiers"; what is version of record?
- Maybe finding previous versions
- Code contributors or license holders should be identified/identifiable in such a way that findability for software includes retrieving software that matches searches like "find me all the code so and so contributed to" - very important in corporate settings and in establishment of prior art etc?
- Do we need a metadata file for each version and subversion of software?
- open source. open source with running docs. I don't care if I can find un-runnable software or compiled binaries with no way to peek under the hood. why find a black box?

Suggestions for other guiding principles relating to findability:

- Metadata should specify how software can be translated between its written and its executable state
- Machine-readable metadata must make all direct and indirect dependencies findable, using version-specific identifiers.
- Metadata describing software have to follow a commonly agreed upon standard.

Other suggestions that don't appear to relate to findability, but may be to other principles:

- Sustainability, e.g. software that is meant to last should be written in formats and languages that are backward compatible. [Interoperable, Reusable]
- Structure and format: care should be taken to use common best practice in code formatting and programming style. No obfuscated Perl! [Reusable]
- Well commented: software should be clearly structured with informative, human readable comments. [Accessible, Reusable]
- Software should be *documented* with openly available documentation that is available even if the code isn't. [Accessible, Reusable]

FAIR Principles (2016)	Towards FAIR Principles for Research Software (2020)	Subgroup 4 survey discussion
<p>F. Findable</p> <p>The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process.</p>		
<p>F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier</p>	<p>F1. Software and its associated metadata have a global, unique and persistent identifier for each released version.</p>	<p>83.9% applies / 16.1% applies but not as written / 0% does not apply</p> <p>Identifiers should not be restricted to releases. Every version, release or not, should ideally be citeable.</p> <p>Suggest rewording to "Software and its associated metadata have a global, unique and persistent identifier." because you might want to identify software which is not the exact release.</p> <p>Identifier should be on the</p>

		software. The version/release/artifact needs "more" than an identifier. Semantic versioning should directly be respected as well as principles of automated generation of artifacts (CI).
F2. Data are described with rich metadata	F2. Software is described with rich metadata.	80.6% applies / 12.9% applies but not as written / 6.5% does not apply The metadata standard should also be stated. Difficult to understand what "rich" means in this context.
F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include identifiers for all the versions of the software it describes.	80.6% applies / 9.7% applies but not as written / 9.7% does not apply May not be useful - enough to have references for previous and next versions. It would be infeasible to request rich metadata for all old versions, some of which might not be runnable anymore.
F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	F4. Software and its associated metadata are included in a searchable software registry.	64.5% applies / 29.0% applies but not as written / 6.5% does not apply The term "software registry" is not well defined, so the application of the principle is unclear. Don't see the strict requirement for a specific software registry [over other mechanisms for searching for software]. Unclear that it has to be a specific software registry, rather than a general research object registry. Code repositories could be

		<p>classed as “searchable software repositories”</p> <p>Cannot be “a” searchable software registry. Metadata should follow standards such that any registry / search engine can use it.</p>
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Accessible

What does accessibility mean in the context of software?

- Open-source licensed
- Uses standard package managers for the specific programming language
- Source code can be retrieved / downloaded and inspected / run / modified locally
 - does not exclude the requirement for registration/payment)
- Accessible through an open repository
- Uses open metadata
- The software (and related objects, including metadata) can be accessed via a dereferenceable/resolvable identifier, using a standard protocol
- Access to documentation describing the use of the software
- Sustainable
 - Can I (continue to) use it for my research? Will the work I do with it be replicable by my future self or others now?
- PID points to a repository which ensures long term storage
 - E.g. Software Heritage
- Ease of installation and use
- Ability to run the software
 - The source code and metadata (e.g. compiler commands and list of dependencies) are not sufficient, a binary version of the compiled software needs to be available in an emulated environment.
 - Access to source code or executables/binaries so that people can execute the software
 - Second-most preference: software doesn't need downloading and/or installation, runs in a browser/shell/GUI
 - Second-most preference: software doesn't need downloading and/or installation, it can be accessed without login credentials (e.g. scientific portals)
 - A platform to run the software still exists
- Clear how to gain access to the software, or failing it, that it can not be accessed (any longer).
- It SHOULD mean making sure software is usable by many people regardless of ability. I'm ashamed how much the A in FAIR is eating up an important guiding principle of software creation.
- Same as it does for FAIR data

Are there any additional guiding principles that apply to software relating to accessibility that should be added?

- “Software should include sufficient information to enable it to be executed”
 - Software should include sufficient information on how to compile it & run it (operate it, even before it is interoperable)
 - System requirements?
- “Software should follow relevant coding standards”
 - The use of clear code structure, clearly commenting code, and following common coding best practices
- “Software should be accessible in the long-term”
 - Accessibility should also refer to long-term access, since with the definition here a GitHub or other dev platform url is enough for access, which is not true (see Gitorious example) - this comment is an extension of the actual FAIR data principle
 - *How can this be reconciled with making all versions identifiable?*
- “Software should be available in an easy-to-use / ready-to-use form”
 - I would add a principle concerning the fact that the software is much more usable if it can be accessed in an easy-to-use form (e.g. installers, containers) rather than only source code with multiple dependencies that might be hard to compile for a large share of users.
- “Any dependencies required by the software should also be FAIR”
 - What about dependencies? Should they be available under the same protocol?
- “Software should address accessibility barriers”
 - These should consider all barriers so that software is usable by as many people as possible. E.g. disabilities, device type, network speed

FAIR Principles (2016)	Towards FAIR Principles for Research Software (2020)	Subgroup 4 survey discussion
A. Accessible Once the user finds the required data, she/he needs to know how can they be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.		
A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	A1. Software and its associated metadata are accessible by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.	77.4% applies / 16.1% applies but not as written / 6.5% does not apply No need to discuss A1 and A2, which are specific to

		<p>issues with research data. We already have standard protocols for accessing software, e.g. HTTP(S)</p> <p>Is a Jupyter Notebook portal a standardized protocol?</p> <p>Better expressed as (Meta)data and code... ?</p> <p>We don't have standard protocols for sharing metadata and it will be difficult with some programming languages.</p>
A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.	<p>83.9% applies / 3.2% applies but not as written / 12.9% does not apply</p> <p>Not sure what this means in a software context.</p>
A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary	A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.	<p>80.0% applies / 6.7% applies but not as written / 13.3% does not apply</p> <p>Not sure what this means in a software context.</p>
A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	A2. Software metadata are accessible, even when the software is no longer available.	<p>86.7% applies / 3.3% applies but not as written / 10.0% does not apply</p> <p>No need to discuss A1 and A2, which are specific to issues with research data. We already have standard protocols for accessing software, e.g. HTTP(S)</p>

Interoperable

What does "interoperability" mean in the context of software?

- Outputs should be machine readable, pipeable
 - The output of software should be directly readable by subsequent software (machine readable) and it should be possible to control the software via api or setting files (GUI should be an add-on, not the primary way to interact with the software)
 - I can run it from a command-line without human interaction, I can 'script' my usage of it, and I can embed it in a workflow.
 - a software tool can be use in a pipeline, allowing other software tools to interact or at least their outputs to interact and be usable
- Software should be able to be used together with other software and data, as part of workflows
 - I find this very difficult to move to a software context, software which needs to be part of a workflow is probably already interoperable and there are not many reasons otherwise in the same way is true of combining data for new insights
 - Being able to use the software together with other pieces of software & data. In other words reading & writing standard (interoperable) formats.
 - Being able to get interconnected to other pieces of software (it does not have to be automatic or so, only be possible) but I am not sure that should be requested for all sort of software
 - Software should be created in a way that allows it to be integrated (fully or in parts) into other workflows or work on other data sets
 - works with other objects, other software
 - Works well - either on its own or via openly accessible tools - with other pieces of software implemented in another language/format
 - That software can be connected to other pieces of software so they work together
 - FAIR software should interoperate with other FAIR software via (meta)data that is FAIR.
 - One Software works with another. In software engineering this is often called composability and there has been lots of research about how to attain it (category theory).
 - That the software integrates well in workflows comprising other tools and dataformats.
- Well-defined and documented input/output formats and APIs, use of existing community standards
 - input and output file formats are defined. APIs are documented. Interface documentation exists. software can be used in workflows
 - use of "standard" datatypes wherever possible, to be used in connection with other tools
 - following certain universal protocols that already exist for articles and data, e.g. use of CrossRef (ORCID profiles, citations), CREDIT author taxonomy, COPE ethical guidelines

- Software and its associated metadata use community-agreed (open) standards
- Data formats for input and output are standardized and reusable in other software;
- Interoperability concerns platforms and software environments - it is about API (application programming interfaces).
- use of standard file formats and well documented APIs
- Compatibility of input and outputs formats
 - Compatibility of input and output formats + Cooperation of the components used in the software itself
- Portability of the resource/data
 - The resource/data could be shared between systems.
 - Easy to install on different machine (from laptop to cluster to cloud)
 - sw can be run (with some adaptations) on similar machines
 - The ability to incorporate the software into another environment, to be able to interface with other software or hardware (with reasonable effort/cost).
- Well-classified
 - Classification in a software ontology, programming language accessibility, build system (e.g. list of dependencies).
- Interoperability should also touch (together with reusable) on the property of usability. FAIR needs to stay usable - not a burden on the authors but a welcoming addition.
- Nothing in general. It is highly context-dependent. At best, interoperability between software and data can be discussed in the existing FAIR framework.
- is the software and metadata about it presented to users and machines/other software in such a way that they can reasonably interact with it ? in the Assessment Report on FAIRness of software the authors echo others who agree that for software guaranteeing interoperability demands attention to dependencies and execution environments
- I think the outcome of integrating one piece of software into another is not the same as integrating data sources. In a sense, all software is "integrated" with, or depends upon other software. And some--but not all--software can be written such that it can be (easily) integrated into other software projects. Getting this right seems to me to a critical component of reuse.
- On the other hand, there is a concept of interoperation between software that does make sense to me, and that is via the (non-dependent) exchange of (meta)data between two or more bits of loosely coupled, independent, "unintegrated" software. This could be file formats accepted by both, or the passing of a stream of (meta)data between to running instance of software. But to be clear, I am excluding the (meta)data exchanged via calls to libraries or similar where one piece of software depends on another and shifting this to "reuse".
- The science code manifesto
 - Code, Copyright, Citation, Credit, Curation
- Be pragmatic

Are there any additional guiding principles that apply to software relating to interoperability that should be added?

- “Software should document the environment required to execute the software”
[should this be in Reusable?]
 - In addition to document dependencies, also the environment required to execute the software (unless it is implicitly included in "dependency")
- “Software should support checkpointing / repetition of runs”
 - Capturing an executable representation of the software which can be used to repeat runs for a long time is not adressed.
- “Software should be linked to related objects including publications using the code, other versions of the code, tools and libraries used, and derived versions of the code”
[should this be in Findable or Reusable?]
 - “The software should be linked to a list of publications using the code, to other versions of the code, to relevant versions of tools and libraries used, and to derived code.”
 - The list of publications is under I3 (which is not considered here)

FAIR Principles (2016)	Towards FAIR Principles for Research Software (2020)	Subgroup 4 survey discussion responses
<p>I. Interoperable The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.</p>		
<p>I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p>	<p>I1. Software and its associated metadata use a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language to facilitate machine readability and data exchange.</p>	<p>67.7% applies / 22.6% applies but not as written / 9.7% does not apply</p> <p>I1: this current statement doesn't take into account that software is all written in a formal language, and so there is some inherent standardisation, the differences come in how that language is used to code up the intent</p> <p>I1. It applies to metadata but I do not see how it applies to software. How many users should have a programming</p>

		<p>language to be FAIRly broad? Machine readable, I do not image a software not being machine readable.</p> <p>I1 - one language might not be enough. metadata language should be interoperable with language used for data. Software interfaces don't exist for data, but there is UML or json schema. Each kind of interoperability might need its own language.</p> <p>I1. For source code-based software, I would say that code quality needs to be considered. For an extreme example, take Javascript code that is minified to reduce the bandwidth on a webpage. The minified code is difficult to audit, even after applying reverse minification. In the context of research software, poorly written code can lead to issues for future users. For example in C++, forgetting to include the STL header for a function or type that is used in a piece of code (thus relying on an indirect include from another, unrelated STL header) can prevent re-use of the software on a platform with a different version of the same compiler, because the STL headers make no guarantee about which other STL headers they indirectly include.</p> <p>Some programming languages have guidelines regarding code quality (e.g. PEP8 for Python or ISO CPP guidelines for C++). There are tools to apply code quality changes automatically (autopep for</p>
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		<p>PEP8 rules, Clang-tidy for C++ rules). There are tools to flag bugprone code and explain what the issue and risks are (e.g. Clang-tidy for C++, pylint for Python, shellcheck for bash). Some of these tools additionally upload your code quality score to a public website where your project is compared against other projects (e.g. lgtm).</p> <p>What does "broadly applicable language to facilitate machine readability and data exchange" mean in terms of software? Controlled vocabularies can be used only the software metadata. What a controlled vocabulary would be for the software itself? The programming language? Sounds odd calling a programming language a controlled vocabulary. Is text/audio data? If yes, then some software (translation/transcription software) does not (necessarily) produce data described by a FAIR controlled vocabulary (unless the software is also producing that metadata; however, I am happy if a transcription software gives me only the transcription with no metadata at all, it all depends how or what for the data will be use). Not sure what mechanisms to access dependencies mean (if is it access as in FAIR maybe yes, it applies as written; although, thinking on FAIR evaluators, there should be no penalties is a dependency --a good one-- is not as FAIR as possible).</p> <p>I1 seems like a fairly</p>
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		<p>vacuous point in the context of software. I don't think we need a principle to guide people to undertake this, because I think it's inherently true of any software (at least, if it compiles). It's still important to communicate to stakeholders like archivists who may not be aware, that software is almost always expressed in a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language.</p>
I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	Reinterpreted, extended and split into I2S.1 and I2S.2	
	<p>I2S.1 Software and its associated metadata are formally described using controlled vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>63.3% applies / 26.7% applies but not as written / 10.0% does not apply</p> <p>I2S1. It applied to metadata but not sure it does for software. What is a controlled vocabulary for software? Is it the programming language? If yes, would any programming language be less FAIR than others?</p> <p>Controlled vocabularies are (and should be) always in progress, adapting to actual community use and practices. Software is immensely flexible and varied, it may happen that the current version of a controlled vocabulary doesn't cover a particular application that still needs documentation. So semi-formal descriptions might have a necessary role.</p> <p>I2S.1 feels to me like it is an element of reuse, not interoperation.</p>

		<p>I2S.1. Software's metadata are formally described using controlled vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.</p>
	<p>I2S.2 Software use and produce data in types and formats that are formally described using controlled vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.</p>	<p>71.0% applies / 29.0% applies but not as written / 0.0% does not apply</p> <p>I2S2. What is the difference here between type and format?</p> <p>I2S.2 more or less describes for me what I think the foundational principle should express, not a sub-principle. But it could be simplified to something like "FAIR software should exchange (meta)data that is FAIR".</p> <p>I2S.2. Software use and produce data that follows the FAIR principles.</p> <p>we should have some sort of vocabulary example</p> <p>Even better than using data in types and formats that are formally described would be the option to use wide-spread standard data types and formats.</p>
<p>I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data</p>	<p>Discarded I3.</p>	
	<p>I4S Software dependencies are documented and mechanisms to access them exist.</p>	<p>87.1% applies / 12.9% applies but not as written / 0.0% does not apply</p> <p>I4S. The important question of long-time access of dependencies is not included in the principle</p> <p>Dependencies describe integration, but don't automatically create the</p>

		preconditions for interoperation. What (I4S) describes should be a principle for (re)use.
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Reusable

What does "reusability" mean in the context of software?

- Ability for others to understand and use for their own purposes
 - The ability for others to run the software for their purposes and having enough understanding to be able to modify it slight for their purposes
 - Being able to use the software for other purpose than the authors originally intended for example with a different data set than the original authors used
 - The resource/data could be reused in different software.
 - Software should be applicable to other problems that were not in the original scope of the software.
 - can be used independently as intended or to extend
 - being able to understand what a software does, and to apply it to similar cases
 - Software can either be run again in its original circumstances, or there is enough info (in e.g. in-line comments) that it can be analysed/picked apart and re-implemented in another language/format
 - Source code easy to read and modify, low to zero error expectation
 - It's the reuse of the software source code for a new implementation, it's not about executing the software and using it
 - More broadly, I can use that software in the future for other similar tasks (e.g. by changing input data or other configuration options)
 - people can use the software in other contexts other than the original purpose intended. For example other environments, other datasets, other times.
 - the ability to download, compile, modify, and run the software.
 - That it can be adapted to match new use cases
 - 1. The possibility to understand exactly what the software does, in order to judge if it is suitable for use in a different context.
 - run the sw on my machine, get the (nearly) same results for the same input data as in the paper and be able to use the software for other data

- Well-documented/curated and easy to run / lower effort than building own
 - Documentation and defined run environments
 - Well documented and readable software are useful for the users and developers.
 - Metadata and comprehensive documentation + suitable licence
 - You can run it at a specific version in an easy to set up environment. Examples for that environment are provided as workflows used in publication. execution environments exist for reviewers.

- any user anywhere in the world with reasonable skills should be able to install and run software, use code
 - can I run it? Do I have the right to run it? will it run? It can mean any of these things which are different considerations than for data
 - The (re)use of software means that the software has been curated in a way that gives it the best possible chance of use on its own, or, in some cases, integrated into another piece of software.
 - The user should be able to use software for their own purpose with an effort that is lower than rewriting the code.
- Reproducibility
 - can rerun software and get reproducible answers for defined inputs
 - The software should be able to reproduce results generated previously, to some extent (stochastic simulation softwares are not expected to reproduce simulation data exactly, but statistics derived from the simulation data should match the published ones).
 - Not sure, it can cover multiple dimensions (repeat, reproduce, reuse). I am happy if I manage to run examples accompanying the software getting the expected results
 - Suitable license
 - Metadata and comprehensive documentation + suitable licence
 - The software should have a license that explains the conditions for re-use.
 - can I run it? Do I have the right to run it? will it run? It can mean any of these things which are different considerations than for data
 - <https://reuse.software/>
 - 2. Clear licenses.
 - Usable and extensible
 - Usability means that the software can be used by the authors and others as intended by its authors (and I think that is enough for FAIRness). Reusability would go forward, for instance being extensible
 - The software should be extensible.
 - Reusability means straightforward packaging of software, open license, being able to base one software on top of (high quality) other software.
 - The ability to change/adapt the software or parts of the software, with reasonable cost/time.
 - Sustainable
 - Minimally: I (or someone else) can use it tomorrow to do with it what I did today.
 - Long-Term - support and updates are required.

Are there any additional guiding principles that apply to software relating to reusability that should be added?

- A principle considering the encapsulation (e.g., modularity, portability, abstraction) and flexibility (e.g., less hard coded variables) of the software would enable greater

reuse. It wouldn't always apply, but then there are other principles where this is already the case (e.g., "authorisation...where necessary").

- To my thinking, the equivalent principle for data is that it should have a plurality of relevant attributes... in other words it's asking the depositor to consider that the data might be used outside the narrow questions they themselves might have considered. The principle is asking for as much context as possible. So the software is asking that others be able to zero in on parts of the software or easily change parameters that the author considered fixed. As with data though, this is an opened ended request, not a mandate.
- In concert with this, a similar or subsequent principle covering the separate treatment of components of a complex software object might also be good. For instance to separate out data objects from software, and to break apart software objects that meaningfully operate independently.
- Additionally usability and long-term support principles, like Code of conduct, contributing, readme, etc. should be explicitly recommended.
- I do think that it is important to stress the need for documentation encapsulating the intent of the software at quite a fine level within the code/human readable formats
- be pragmatic
- Clear and detailed documentation is necessary, both in-line in the code and as a separate document
- Separate documentation for developers and users
- No documentation of static vs. dynamic correctness is mentioned.

FAIR Principles (2016)	Towards FAIR Principles for Research Software (2020)	Subgroup 4 survey discussion
<p>R. Reusable The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.</p>		
<p>R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</p>	<p>R1. Software and its associated metadata are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.</p>	<p>71% applies / 22.6% applies but not as written / 6.5% does not apply</p> <p>R1 has the same problem that the original principle has: what is rich and plural?</p> <p>R1.2 and R1.3 requires communities but no where there a definition of what a FAIR community is. Provenance is also kind of</p>

		<p>standard I would say due to references, citations and journals, not sure why the community is needed here, looks like there is already a standard there.</p> <p>R1: "Software...[is] richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes" makes no sense to me. The metadata that describes software should be, but what does this mean within the software?</p> <p>R1: This sounds like "the more, the better". However, such rich data needs to be maintained as well, or it will be even worse than no metadata. Maybe add "up-to-date" as first requirement and the others after that as "secondary" (as much data as possible without losing "up-to-dateness").</p> <p>R1. Not sure what attributes refers to here.</p> <p>Software and its associated metadata are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. -> ontology tagged software doesn't really increase its utility to me.</p>
<p>R1.1 (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license</p>	<p>R1.1 Software and its associated metadata have independent, clear and accessible usage licenses compatible with the software dependencies.</p>	<p>96.8% applies / 3.2% applies but not as written / 0% does not apply</p>
<p>R1.2 (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance</p>	<p>R1.2 Software metadata include detailed provenance, detail level should be community agreed.</p>	<p>83.9% applies / 16.1% applies but not as written / 0% does not apply</p> <p>R1.2 the phrase "detail level should be community</p>

		<p>agreed" just restates R1.3</p> <p>Community standards are (and should be) in constant development. Exceptions to following the standards should be possible when e.g. it is necessary to give more information that the template asks for. I would like to rephrase it as R1.2 "Software metadata include detailed provenance, detail level should be at least as high as the community agreed best practice."</p> <p>R1.2: Provenance for software is authorship. Best ensured by version control.</p>
<p>R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards</p>	<p>Software metadata and documentation meet domain-relevant community standards.</p>	<p>87.1% applies / 12.9% applies but not as written / 0% does not apply</p> <p>R1.3 if not timebound may be problematic?</p> <p>Community standards are (and should be) in constant development. Exceptions to following the standards should be possible when e.g. it is necessary to give more information that the template asks for. I would like to rephrase it as R1.3 "Software metadata and documentation meet or rise above domain-relevant community standards."</p> <p>Community standards is quite fuzzy and dangerous.</p> <p>R1.3 there should be an interdisciplinary minimum standard. Only this way you will be able to find software which has generalisation built in</p>

References

1. FAIR4RS WG. (2021). FAIR4RS Subgroup 4 - reading list of new research (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4555865>